

Supplementary information about q-Gaussian Tsallis line shapes for Raman spectroscopy

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Abstract

q-Gaussians are probability distributions having their origin in the framework of Tsallis statistics. A continuous real parameter q is characterizing them so that, in the range $1 < q < 3$, the q -functions pass from the usual Gaussian form, for q close to 1, to the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution for $q=2$. For q greater than 2, the distribution is a heavily tailed one. This behavior of q -Gaussian functions can be used for the analysis of Raman spectra, instead of Gaussian, Lorentzian or Voigt profiles. In a first part of our research, we have provided several simulations and examples of q -Gaussian fitted Raman spectra and related band deconvolution. Here we continue the research work, providing supplementary information about the use of q -Gaussians, mainly considering the study of isolated bands.

Keywords: q-Gaussian distribution, Gaussian distribution, Cauchy distribution, Lorentzian distribution, Voigt distribution, Tsallis line shape, Tsallis entropy.

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In Raman spectroscopy Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles are the line shapes most used to fit the spectral bands. However, the real Raman lines seldom follow these specific cases (Kirillov, 2004). To improve the analysis, the Voigt profiles are often used (Meier, 2005). Instead of the Voigt profile, Sparavigna, 2023 (a)-(d), proposed the use of q -Gaussian functions. The q -Gaussian functions are probability distributions of Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, Hanel et al., 2009). These functions are based on a generalized form of the exponential function (see for instance Sparavigna, 2022), with a continuous real parameter q characterizing them. In the range $1 < q < 3$, the q -Gaussian functions pass from the usual Gaussian form, for q close to 1, to the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution for $q=2$. For q greater than 2, the q -Gaussian becomes a heavy-tailed function. As the Voigt profile, the q -Gaussian function is giving a line shape which is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profiles in general.

Several successful applications of q -Gaussians in fitting Raman data have been proposed (Sparavigna 2023 (b)), mainly concentrated on the deconvolution of the spectrum in component bands. Continuing our research, we consider here the study of isolated bands, to obtain supplementary information about the use of q -Gaussians in Raman spectroscopy. In the article by Robert Meier, 2005, where the author proposed "some crucial issues in curve-fitting vibrational spectra that do not always seem respected", we can find told that there is no problem in handling the isolated bands. "Problems arise when there is band overlap" (Meier, 2005). Problems exist also with isolated bands, since the profile is usually different from the Gaussian or the Lorentzian profile. The study of the isolated bands for what is regarding the behavior of q -Gaussian fitting is therefore fundamental. As previously told, to Gaussian or Lorentzian profiles, it is sometimes preferred the Voigt profile. Then, let us start from fitting q -Gaussian functions over experimental data, compared with Voigt function fitting.

1. Comparison with Voigt fitting

Thibault et al., 2002, studied the Raman linewidth of CO in Ar, using an inverse Raman spectrometer. In the Figure 1 of their article, the Raman spectrum of the Q(5) line is given. In the upper field of the figure, we can find Voigt profile fitted over the experimental spectrum. The lower field of the figure is giving the difference between experimental data and Voigt profile.

Let us consider the data in the Figure 1 by Thibault et al., 2002, and fit to a q-Gaussian function. The result is given in the following Figure 1.

Fig.1: In red, the experimental data from Thibault et al., 2002; in green, the q-Gaussian best fit (q-parameter, $q=1.775$). In the lower part of the figure, it is given the difference between the red and the green lines. The two black lines are giving the band of uncertainty of experimental data (the width of the band is 0.012 in the y-axis scale). Note that the difference is within the band. For what is regarding the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 270 data points).

Where is the main difference between the use of q-Gaussian profile and Voigt profile? First, the q-Gaussian is a probability distribution having an analytic form. The Voigt function is the convolution of two functions, Gaussian and Lorentzian, with no associated analytic form. The analytic q-Gaussian is characterized by the presence of the q-parameter. The width of its profile is provided by a single simple expression (see the Width at Half Maximum in the Appendix here given). To characterize the width of a profile fitted to Voigt functions, two parameters are required, one related to the Gaussian the other to the Lorentzian component of convolution.

Let us also consider the work by Huang et al., 2014, where the role of the substrate about the analysis of graphene Raman lineshapes is investigated. The researchers fitted “the bandwidths of G-band and 2D-band ... into the Voigt profile ... The bandwidths of Lorentzian parts were kept as constant whether it is the suspended and supported graphene. For the Gaussian part, the suspended graphene exhibits much greater Gaussian bandwidths than those of the supported graphene” (Huang et al., 2014). “With data fitting into Voigt profile, one can find out the information behind the lineshapes. ... Under our analysis, details about the effects of charged impurities on the substrate can be realized. About the strain effect or doping effect on graphene, some possible broadening mechanisms may still be responsible for deforming it, so we considered the Gaussian profile necessary” (Huang et al., 2014). “Based on the data fitting results, the analysis of measured point across the graphene surface, the bandwidths of Gaussian profiles and Lorentzian profiles given by Voigt fitting is presented in Figure 4a,b” (the figure is in Huang et al., 2014). In the mentioned article, it is also stressed that the “Lorentzian bandwidth is mainly contributed by the natural linewidth and partly from the uncertainty of data fitting ... and instrumental uncertainty ... The natural linewidth is just linked with the phonon lifetimes between interaction levels” (Huang et al., 2014).

We can use data from Figure 4a,b in Huang et al., 2014 and fit q-Gaussians over them. We find that the q-parameter of the Raman spectrum of the suspended graphene is lower than the q-parameter of the spectrum of the supported graphene.

Fig.2: In red, the experimental data from Huang et al., 2014, Fig.4a (supported graphene). In green, the q-Gaussian best fit (q-parameter, $q=1.64$). In the lower part of the figure, it is given the difference between the red and the green lines. The two black lines are giving the band of uncertainty of experimental data (the width of the band is 0.02 in the y-axis scale). Note that the difference is almost within the band. On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 270 data points).

Fig.3: In red, the experimental data from Huang et al., 2014, Fig.4b (suspended graphene). In green, the q-Gaussian best fit (q-parameter, $q=1.48$). In the lower part of the figure, it is given the difference between the red and the green lines. The two black lines are giving the band of uncertainty of experimental data (the width of the band is maintained equal to 0.02, in the y-axis scale, as in the Figure 2). Note that the difference is almost within the band. On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 270 data points).

We can decompose the two q-Gaussians given in Figs.2 and 3, in the sum of a Gaussian ($q=1.01$) and a Lorentzian ($q=2.0$). Note that q-value 1.01 is giving a q-Gaussian which is a function numerically indistinguishable from the corresponding Gaussian function. The two decompositions are given in the following figure.

Fig. 4: Decomposition of the two q-Gaussians in the sum of a Gaussian and a Lorentzian function. In red, the q-Gaussian, in green the best fit obtained with the sum. Note please that the q-Gaussian is not a pseudo-Voigt function (that is a linear combination Gaussian and Lorentzian functions). This explains the negligible numerical difference between q-Gaussian and best fit.

Fig. 5: Decomposition of q-Gaussians with different q-parameters (σ is the same, see Appendix for definition) in the sum of a Gaussian and a Lorentzian function. In red, the q-Gaussian, in green the best fit obtained by means of the sum. The Gaussian component is represented by the blue profile and the Lorentzian one by the magenta profile. The areas under the Gaussian and Lorentzian functions can be used as the relative weight of the components.

As shown in the Figure 5, the q-parameter can be related to the relative weight of the Gaussian and Lorentzian components. The simplest evaluation could be made by integration, that is, by the area under the two curves, blue and magenta in the Figure 5.

2. Zinc and zinc acetate

In Ghazvini et al., 2016, the researchers are reporting on the electrodeposition of zinc from the ionic liquid 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate with various concentrations of zinc acetate. Raman spectroscopy was used to study the coordination of Zn^{2+} ions with OAc^- (Ghazvini et al., 2016). In the Figure 6 of Ghazvini et al., 2016, we can find the Raman spectra of $[EMIm]OAc$ at different concentrations of $Zn(OAc)_2$ in the wavenumber range between 880 and 940 cm^{-1} . In the Figure 7, the researchers provide the deconvolution of some of these Raman spectra by two Voigt functions. Here, let us consider the data from the Figure 7 and proposed a deconvolution obtained by means of two q-Gaussians. Here the results in the following plots.

Fig.6: In red, the experimental data from Ghazvini et al., 2016). In green, the q-Gaussian best fit. On the right, the two components are given with the related q-parameters. On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 250 data points). In the case of the upper image, we can see that the best fit is giving a value of q-parameter which is slightly larger than 2 (this is probably due to a small shift of the baseline).

3. Synthetic Organic Pigments

In Sparavigna, 2023b, we started the fitting examples with spectra of the SOPRANO database (<https://soprano.kikirpa.be/index.php?lib=sop>, Fremout & Saverwyns, 2012). Data are given according to the Creative Common Attribution, NonCommercial, NoDerivatives 4.0 License (many thanks to Wim Fremout, Coordinator, and people working in the project). Let us add here some further examples. In the following figures, some bands of the sample PR2 (chemical class: Naphthol AS), available at the following link https://soprano.kikirpa.be/index.php?lib=sop&id=PR2_A_785_kikirpa

Fig.7: In red, experimental data PR2 from SOPRANO, in green, the q-Gaussian fitting the data (left). Components given with values of q-parameters (right). On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 340 data points).

Fig.8: In red, experimental data PR2 from SOPRANO, in green, the q-Gaussian fitting the data (up). Components and values of q-parameters (down). On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integer n (series of 290 data points).

Fig.9: In red, experimental data PR2 from SOPRANO, in green, the q-Gaussian fitting the data (left). Components and values of q-parameters (right). On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integers n (series of 150 data points).

Fig.10: In red, the experimental data PR2 from SOPRANO, in green, the q-Gaussian fitting the data (left). Components and values of q-parameters (right). On the x-axis, data are given as a function of integers n (series of 400 data points).

Fig. 11

In the Figure 11, we assume just a part of the band given in Fig., to enhance the role of main component. We fit (green) the q-Gaussian over data (red). A convenient scale is used for y-axis. The value of q-parameter is slightly changing.

Appendix

As given by Umarov et al., 2008, the q-Gaussian function is: $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a scale constant. In the exponent, we use $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$. The q-exponential has the expression:

$$exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)} \quad (2).$$

The plots in the Figures A1 and A2 are showing the behaviour of this exponential for different q values. Note that, for q less than one, the function is different from zero on a limited interval.

Fig. A1: q - exponential functions, where the blue curve is representing a Lorentzian function ($q=2$). The pink curve corresponds to $q=1.5$ and light blue to $q= 1.01$, practically a Gaussian function. The green curve is the q -Gaussian for $q=0.75$ and red curve for $q=0.5$. For $q < 1$, the function is different from zero in a limited interval. Being the line symmetric, only the right part of it is given in the figure.

The Half Width at Half Maximum of q line shape is given by: $\sqrt{2} \sigma \sqrt{(1 - (1/2)^{1-q})/(1 - q)}$.

Fig. A2: q - exponential functions for $q=1.01$ and $q=2$ on the left, on the right the Half Width at Half Maximum as a function of q .

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